

Monitoring of toxic cyanobacterial blooms in Lalla Takerkoust reservoir by satellite imagery and microcystin transfer to surrounding farms

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ABSTRACT

Cyanobacterial harmful algal blooms (CyanoHABs) threaten public health and freshwater ecosystems worldwide. In this study, our main goal was to explore the dynamics of cyanobacterial blooms and how microcystins (MCs) move from the Lalla Takerkoust reservoir to the nearby farms. We used Landsat imagery, molecular analysis, collecting and analyzing physicochemical data, and assessing toxins using HPLC. Our investigation identified two cyanobacterial species responsible for the blooms: *Microcystis* sp. and *Synechococcus* sp. Our *Microcystis* strain produced three MC variants (MC-RR, MC-YR, and MC-LR), with MC-RR exhibiting the highest concentrations in dissolved and intracellular toxins. In contrast, our *Synechococcus* strain did not produce any detectable toxins. To validate our Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) results, we utilized limnological data, including algal cell counts, and quantified MCs in freeze-dried *Microcystis* bloom samples collected from the reservoir. Our study revealed patterns and trends in cyanobacterial proliferation in the reservoir over 30 years and presented a historical map of the area of cyanobacterial infestation using the NDVI method. The study found that MC-LR accumulates near the water surface due to the buoyancy of *Microcystis*. The maximum concentration of MC-LR in the reservoir water was 160 µg L⁻¹. In contrast, 4 km downstream of the reservoir, the concentration decreased by a factor of 5.39 to 29.63 µg L⁻¹, indicating a decrease in MC-LR concentration with increasing distance from the bloom source. Similarly, the MC-YR concentration decreased by a factor of 2.98 for the same distance. Interestingly, the MC distribution varied with depth, with MC-LR dominating at the water surface and MC-YR at the reservoir outlet at a water depth of 10 m. Our findings highlight the impact of nutrient concentrations, environmental factors, and transfer processes on bloom dynamics and MC distribution. We emphasize the need for effective management strategies to minimize toxin transfer and ensure public health and safety.

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1. Introduction

Cyanobacterial harmful algal blooms (CyanoHABs) constitute growing concerns in freshwater ecosystems worldwide, particularly in developing countries (Mohamed, 2016; Teta et al., 2021). These blooms result from the proliferation of specific cyanobacteria—a type of prokaryotic photosynthetic microorganisms. While many species of cyanobacteria are non-toxic, some can produce a variety of toxins, including microcystins (MCs), which can pose severe risks to human and animal health (Chorus et al., 2021; Manganelli et al., 2023). The presence of toxin-producing strains is particularly worrisome, as CyanoHABs—fueled by eutrophication and climate change—can lead to the release of MCs into water sources used for drinking water but also for agricultural irrigation, posing potential risks to crops and human health (Czyżewska et al., 2020; Spooft et al., 2020; Xiang et al., 2019).

To address these concerns, it is essential to understand the dynamics of MCs transfer from water bodies such as contaminated reservoirs to end users, particularly farmers located at varying distances (Montero et al., 2021). Limited studies have specifically addressed the behavior of MCs concentrations during the transfer process and the underlying processes responsible for this phenomenon, making it a crucial area of investigation. Recent studies have shown that physical and chemical processes such as adsorption, photodegradation, and microbial degradation can influence the fate and transport of MCs during water transfer (Dziga et al., 2013; Gao et al., 2022; Mrdjen and Lee, 2018; Mutoti et al., 2022; Redouane et al., 2019; Song, 2006; Wang et al., 2024).

Understanding the diversity of cyanobacterial species and their interactions is critical for comprehending the complexities of bloom formation and toxin production. Molecular techniques, including DNA sequencing and phylogenetic analysis, have been instrumental in identifying and characterizing cyanobacteria, such as *Microcystis*, a potent producer of MCs (Lezcano et al., 2019; Saleem et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2022). Likewise, other cyanobacterial species from different genera have been identified as MC producers, including *Planktothrix*, *Anabaena*, *Nostoc*, *Oscillatoria*, and *Hapalosiphon* species (Akyol et al., 2021; Nowruzi and Porzani, 2021; Oudra et al., 2009; Wang et al., 2023). Each species possesses unique characteristics influencing their ability to produce and release MCs, emphasizing the importance of understanding their roles in bloom formation and toxin production (Pestana et al., 2020). Recent advances in metagenomic sequencing have increased our abilities to explore toxic cyanobacterial communities by identifying novel species and unveiling new toxin biosynthesis pathways (Rantala et al., 2004). This technological progress has overcome limitations inherent in traditional methods, such as culturing-dependent approaches. It allows for a more comprehensive exploration of toxic cyanobacterial communities, thereby enhancing the understanding of the intricacies involved in bloom formation and toxin production.

Various analytical methods have been developed for detecting and quantifying cyanotoxins in water samples. High-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) coupled with different detectors, such as UV, mass spectrometer (MS), and photodiode array (PDA) (Bouaïcha et al., 2019; Douma et al., 2010; Oudra et al., 2009; Teta et al., 2021), are commonly used for the measurement of cyanobacterial toxins. Additionally, the enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) is another widely used method for detecting cyanotoxins.

The rise of remote sensing technologies, particularly satellite imagery, has become invaluable for monitoring cyanobacterial proliferation in inland waters (Song et al., 2022). Utilizing satellite-based platforms, such as Landsat and MODIS (Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer) imagery, offers a comprehensive and cost-effective approach to assessing historical contamination patterns and identifying the spatial and temporal dynamics of cyanobacterial blooms (Han, 2022; Kumar et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2022; Sayers et al., 2019; Shi et al., 2019). Despite the critical importance of these technologies, there is a scarcity of studies conducted and implemented in developing countries, especially in the African context, to monitor cyanobacterial contamination in

freshwater using satellite imagery.

The accurate identification of algal blooms in water relies on the recognition of light spectra reflectance at wavelengths ranging from red to infrared (630 nm to 900 nm). Images captured at these specific wavelengths offer insights into vegetation cover and overall health (Qin et al., 2022). The monitoring of cyanobacterial blooms leverages this principle to detect floating vegetation on the water's surface. The Normalized Vegetation Index (NDVI) is a commonly employed method for this purpose. However, studies utilizing the NDVI method encounter limitations, such as interference with aquatic plants that can bias readings. These limitations can be addressed by validating NDVI findings with on-site limnological data, including cyanobacteria abundances, quantified cyanotoxins, and chlorophyll content (Ogashawara et al., 2016; Rolim et al., 2023).

Several studies have employed Landsat surface reflectance data to detect and monitor cyanobacterial blooms in water bodies, confirming the effectiveness of NDVI as an indicator for detecting cyanobacterial blooms (Aubriot et al., 2020; Germán et al., 2020; Kumar et al., 2020; Lekki et al., 2019; Sayers et al., 2019; Song et al., 2022; Zhao et al., 2022; Zong et al., 2019). These studies highlight the utility of Landsat images for frequent monitoring of cyanobacterial blooms.

The primary objective of this comprehensive study is to investigate the dynamics of cyanobacterial blooms and the transfer of MCs in the Lalla Takerkoust reservoir, as well as their implications for agricultural fields through irrigation practices. By employing advanced techniques, including Landsat imagery, molecular analysis, physicochemical sampling, and statistical methods, this research aims to achieve four key objectives. Firstly, using multi-sensor Landsat imagery (Landsat 5, 7, and 8), the study seeks to calculate the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) and establish a historical record of cyanobacterial activity in the reservoir spanning 30 years, to identify patterns and trends in cyanobacterial proliferation (1). Secondly, through the isolation and characterization of cyanobacteria, mainly those responsible for the persistent proliferation, the study aims to assess their potential toxicity, thereby shedding light on the risks associated with cyanobacterial blooms and identifying potential health hazards (2). Thirdly, physicochemical sampling was conducted along the entire water route, ranging from the reservoir to the farthest locations where irrigation occurs, to comprehensively evaluate water quality characteristics, including MC levels, and provide an in-depth understanding of toxin distribution and potential risks throughout the irrigation process (3). Lastly, employing robust statistical analysis, the study will examine toxin behavior during the transfer from the reservoir to end users to identify factors influencing toxin reduction or persistence, providing valuable insights for effective management strategies (4).

2. Material and methods

2.1. Landsat image acquisition and processing

To study the Lalla Takerkoust reservoir in Morocco, Landsat 5, 7, and 8 images were acquired from the USGS Earth Explorer portal (<https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov/>). A total of 183 cloud-free images were downloaded annually between 1991 and 2021, spanning from September to March. This timeframe was selected to align with the reservoir's annual bloom presence, which typically occurs during this period due to optimal environmental conditions such as water temperature and nutrient availability. Our decision was further supported by our visual observations, which confirmed the absence of blooms during other times of the year. Additionally, this chosen period corresponds with the availability of collected limnological data, which is crucial for validating the accuracy of satellite results.

We downloaded pre-processed Landsat Collection 2 Level-2 Science Products, which underwent atmospheric correction to produce usable data. The Landsat 8 Operational Land Imager (OLI) surface reflectance products are generated using the Land Surface Reflectance Code (LaSRC)

algorithm (Version 1.5.0) (Vermote et al., 2018). Meanwhile, the Landsat 5 Thematic Mapper (TM) and Landsat 7 Enhanced Thematic Mapper (ETM+) surface reflectance products are generated using the Landsat Ecosystem Disturbance Adaptive Processing System (LEDAPS) algorithm (Version 3.4.0) (Svejar and Dunovsky, 1981).

We applied a scale factor of 0.0000275 and an additional offset of -0.2 per pixel to the Landsat Level-2 surface reflectance data to use the obtained products. To calculate the normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) from the Landsat images, we used the formula:

$$NDVI = \frac{(NIR - RED)}{(NIR + RED)}$$

Where NIR is the near-infrared band, RED is the red band.

By performing NDVI calculations for every year, we created a yearly NDVI map of the Lalla Takerkoust reservoir using the R software.

The spatial resolution of Landsat images varies based on the satellite used. Both Landsat 5 and Landsat 7 have a spatial resolution of 30 m for the visible and near-infrared (NIR) bands. However, Landsat 8 introduced an enhanced sensor with improved capabilities. Landsat 8 maintains a 30 m spatial resolution for the visible and NIR bands while also providing a panchromatic band with a higher spatial resolution of 15 m.

Landsat imagery stands out as a superior option compared to other publicly available platforms like MODIS due to its superior resolution

and scene width. With a spatial resolution of 30 m, Landsat offers finer detail, significantly enhancing the research perspective. Additionally, Landsat scenes cover a width of 185 km, providing a more comprehensive view compared to MODIS, which features variable spatial resolutions (250, 500, or 1000 m) and a broader scene width of 2330 km. Algae contain pigments, such as chlorophyll, Phycocyanin, and phycobiliproteins, that can absorb and reflect light in different parts of the spectrum. Like in vegetation, chlorophyll absorbs and reflects strongly in the red and NIR parts of the spectrum, respectively. However, the reflectance properties of algae in the NIR part of the spectrum can be much lower than vegetation on land.

To process the Landsat images, specific libraries such as sp, raster, rgdal, rgeos, leaflet, RColorBrewer, reshape2, ggplot2, sf, psych, openxlsx, csv, and dplyr were utilized. These libraries provided functions for spatial operations, raster processing, data visualization, data analysis, and file input/output, streamlining the image processing tasks.

After the Landsat images were processed, the distribution of NDVI over time values was assessed. This was done by generating a boxplot of all NDVI values for each year using the R package "ggplot2" (Wickham, 2016). The boxplots were then used to identify each year's median, quartiles, and outliers of the NDVI distribution.

The percentage of the area covered by vegetation was then calculated from the NDVI maps. It was plotted as a heatmap to better present the spatial distribution of bloom cover over time. Finally, the NDVI maps, boxplots, and heatmaps were used to identify the trends in

Fig. 1. Geographic location of Lalla Takerkoust reservoir in Al Haous-Tansift Basin, Morocco, with 4 km water transfer infrastructure (purple line) connecting sample sites: reservoir, dam-exit, and farm.

vegetation cover and cyanobacterial bloom events in the Lalla Takerkoust reservoir and the surrounding region. These analyses revealed changes in vegetation cover over time and the occurrence of cyanobacterial bloom events in the reservoir in certain years.

Overall, using specific libraries for image processing and data analysis allowed for a streamlined and efficient workflow. The resulting visualizations provided a clear view of the temporal distribution of vegetation cover and the occurrence of cyanobacterial blooms, which can be helpful for monitoring and managing the Lalla Takerkoust reservoir and its surrounding region.

2.2. Physico-chemical analysis and alga counts in the Lalla Takerkoust reservoir

The Lalla Takerkoust reservoir is situated in the Al Houz-Tansift Basin of the Marrakech-Safi Region in Morocco, located precisely at 31°21'8.80"N latitude and 8°8'25.03"W longitude (Fig. 1). This reservoir serves multiple crucial functions, including providing irrigation water for nearby farmland, generating electricity, and supplying water for diverse human activities, ranging from recreational uses such as swimming to domestic uses like laundry and, to a certain extent, dish washing. We collected water samples from three locations using sterile one-liter polyethylene bottles to investigate the reservoir's water quality. The first sample was collected from the water surface at a depth of 0.2 m at 31°20'57.36"N and 8°08'22.09"W.

Furthermore, the second sample was procured from the reservoir's outlet, precisely located at coordinates 31°21'17.66"N and 8°08'8.38"W. This site serves as the point of water withdrawal from the reservoir for irrigation purposes and is situated approximately 10 m below the reservoir's water surface (Figure S1). Subsequently, the third sample was gathered 4 km downstream from the reservoir, at a depth of 0.2 m on a farm with coordinates 31°20'22.6"N and 8°07'16.7"W. This particular farm relies on water for crop irrigation. All samples were collected using stringent sterile techniques to prevent contamination, ensuring the reliability and accuracy of the results.

The water sampling was carried out monthly from September to March for each year, spanning from 2019 to 2021. After collection, all samples were transported to the laboratory on ice within 4 h.

In this study, we specifically focused on counting cyanobacteria and green algae due to their distinct spectral responses in the Landsat satellite's captured spectrum, particularly in the red to near-infrared range (600 nm to 880 nm). This wavelength region is acknowledged for its sensitivity to variations in chlorophyll content. The selection of these algal groups was driven by their potential to exhibit spectral characteristics that can be effectively detected and analyzed using remote sensing techniques. Our objective, by concentrating on cyanobacteria and green algae, was to capture and analyze their specific contributions to the overall dynamics of algal blooms in the Lalla Takerkoust reservoir.

To quantify the abundance of cyanobacteria and microscopic green algae in reservoir water samples, aliquots of 0.5 ml were prepared from each sample and placed in 1 ml Eppendorf tubes. The samples underwent rapid disruption through low-power ultrasonic vibration (20 kHz for 5 s) (Latour et al., 2004; Samoudi et al., 2016) to achieve dissociation without damaging the cells. Algal cells in each sample were estimated by cell counting using a Malassez cell counting chamber under an optical microscope (Motic BA210, China) at a magnification of $\times 400$. The algal cell density was calculated according to Tazart et al. (2019) using the formula:

$$\text{Algal cell density (cells L}^{-1}\text{)} = \text{Mean}(Xs) \times 10^8$$

where Mean(Xs) represents the average number of cells counted in 10 squares, with the volume of each square being 0.01 μl .

The Physicochemical parameters of the water samples were analyzed according to standard methods (Gilcreas, 1967). Ammonium ($\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$) and nitrate ($\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$) concentrations were analyzed via the salicylate

method (APHA, 2012). The chemical oxygen demand (COD) was determined using the open reflux method with potassium dichromate as the oxidizing agent (Gilcreas, 1967). Nitrite ($\text{NO}_2\text{-N}$) concentrations were determined by spectrophotometry (APHA, 2012). The total nitrogen (TN) concentrations were determined via the Kjeldahl methods (Gilcreas, 1967). Orthophosphate ($\text{PO}_4\text{-P}$) concentrations were measured via the ascorbic acid method (Gilcreas, 1967), and Total phosphorous (TP) concentrations were analyzed via the spectrophotometric method as orthophosphate after mineralization (Gilcreas, 1967). The pH was measured with a pH meter (Mettler Toledo, Switzerland), and the dissolved oxygen (DO) with an oxygen meter (Hach, USA). The electrical conductivity (EC) and total dissolved solids (TDS) were measured with Hanna HI 9829 multiparameter probes (Hanna Instruments, USA). The 5-day biochemical oxygen demand (BOD_5) was determined using the Winkler method (Gilcreas, 1967). The temperature was measured with a digital thermometer (Hanna Instruments, USA). Finally, all measurements were performed in quadruplicate.

2.3. Comprehensive approach for cyanobacteria isolation, molecular characterization, and microcystin analysis

2.3.1. Cyanobacteria isolation and molecular characterization

During the bloom period from September to December 2019 and November 2020 to February 2021, we collected cyanobacteria biomass samples from the Lalla Takerkoust reservoir using a plankton net with a mesh size of 20 μm . We employed the agar plate method to isolate cyanobacteria from phytoplankton biomass, as described by Zerrifi et al. (2021). The sample used for cyanobacteria isolation was collected on November 11th, 2020. Genomic DNA was extracted from a cyanobacteria pure culture using the chloroform and isoamyl alcohol-based method after Barbier et al. (2019). The 16S rRNA gene was amplified by PCR using specific primers CYA106F (5'-CGGACGGGTGAGTAACGCGTGA-3') and CYA781R (5'-GACTACTGGGGTATCTAATCCATT-3'), which were designed to amplify the cyanobacteria-specific region of the 16S rRNA (Nübel et al., 1997). After PCR amplification, PCR products were checked for purity using agarose gel electrophoresis and Midori Green staining (Abid et al., 2022). The gel was carefully examined to identify PCR products with the desired size and purity for further analysis. The purified PCR products were sent to Macrogen, Switzerland, for sequencing using the same primers used for PCR amplification. At the company, PCR products were again purified using a commercially available kit to remove any remaining contaminants before sequencing.

To systematically investigate the molecular characterization of cyanobacteria strains responsible for toxic blooms in the Lalla Takerkoust reservoir, the initial step involved obtaining consensus sequences of the 16S rRNA gene. This was achieved using SeqTrace 0.9.0 software (Stucky, 2012). Subsequently, the acquired consensus sequences were deposited in the NCBI GenBank database under the accession numbers OQ658601—OQ658602.

To further assess the similarity between cyanobacteria strains from the Lalla Takerkoust reservoir and their nearest clustering neighbors, the BLASTn program in the NCBI database was employed. This comparative analysis utilized a dataset comprising 18 nucleotide sequences. These sequences underwent alignment using the MUSCLE software in MEGA11 (Tamura et al., 2021).

For the phylogenetic analysis, the neighbor-joining method in MEGA 11 software (Tamura et al., 2021) was chosen to compute a robust phylogenetic tree. The methodology included the application of the maximum likelihood method with the Kimura 2-parameter model, supported by 1000 bootstrap replicates. The dataset comprised 1493 positions, and a systematic removal of ambiguous positions was carried out through pairwise deletion.

The resulting optimal tree, representing the evolutionary relationships among cyanobacteria strains, was then evaluated based on bootstrap values converted to percentages. To enhance clarity and conciseness, branches that represented partitions replicated in less than

50 % of the bootstrap replicates were collapsed. Additionally, one single sequence of *Anabaena variabilis* (AY768387.1) was included as an outgroup.

2.3.2. Cyanobacteria biomass collection, MC extraction and analysis

Bloom biomass samples were collected monthly over three years, from September to December 2019 and November 2020 to February 2021, from the surface of the Lalla Takerkoust reservoir. A plankton net with a mesh size of 20 μm was used to collect the cyanobacterial bloom biomass, which was then immediately transferred to the laboratory on ice and lyophilized for preservation.

Cyanobacteria strains were cultured in 1 L Erlenmeyer flasks containing Z8 medium (Javadikasgari et al., 2018) under controlled conditions, with a temperature of 26 ± 2 °C, light intensity of $4000 \text{ lx} \cdot \text{m}^{-2} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, and a photoperiod cycle of 15 h light and 9 h dark for ten days. Aliquots of 4 mL of the cyanobacterial cultures were filtered using a Foxx Life Sciences polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) Syringe Filter with a pore size of 0.22 μm to remove unwanted particles and debris (Foxx Life Sciences, Cole-Parmer GmbH, Germany). Toxins were then extracted from the filtrates. Furthermore, cultures were lyophilized to obtain cyanobacterial biomass material for further toxin extraction.

To extract MCs from the natural bloom samples and the cyanobacterial biomass cultivated in the laboratory, an aqueous extraction method based on El Khaloufi et al. (2012) was used. This method involved an additional step of cell lysis in liquid nitrogen, followed by sonication at 42 kHz, 130 w for 5 min on ice. According to Triantis et al. (2016), the extraction volume was adjusted to 1 % of methanol. The extracts were kept at 4 °C for an overnight extraction. Afterwards, the extracts were filtered using a 33 mm diameter hydrophilic PTFE syringe filter with a pore size of 0.22 μm (Foxx Life Sciences, Cole-Parmer GmbH, Germany).

The bloom filtrates, lab-cultured cyanobacterial biomass filtrates were pre-purified on LiChrolut C-18 cartridges (LiChrolut® RP-18, 40–63 μm , 0.2 g/ 3 mL, Sigma-Aldrich, Munich, Germany), according to Triantis et al. (2017). The cartridges were prepared by pre-conditioning with 4 mL of HPLC-grade methanol followed by 4 mL of ultrapure water before filtering the samples through them. Subsequently, after the samples had passed through the cartridges, they were rinsed with aqueous methanol (20 %). Elution, following the method described by Triantis et al. (2016) with slight modifications, involved using 80 % methanol.

2.3.3. Dissolved MC extraction and analysis

Upon arrival at the laboratory, water samples underwent processing. The pre-purification step involved adding HPLC-grade methanol to the sample and adjusting it to 1 % v/v with ultrapure water. These samples were then filtered through Whatman microfiber glass filter paper GF/C, with a diameter of 47 mm.

The dissolved MCs were further pre-purified using LiChrolut C-18 cartridges (LiChrolut® RP-18, 40–63 μm , 0.2 g/3 mL, Sigma-Aldrich, Munich, Germany). The cartridges were preconditioned with 4 mL of HPLC-grade methanol, followed by 4 mL of ultrapure water before passing the samples through them, following the procedure outlined by Triantis et al. (2016). MCs were quantified using LC-posESI-MS/MS (Vantage, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Massachusetts, USA), applying the

multiple reaction monitoring mode. Table 1 gives the detected m/z values. Separation was achieved using an XSelect HSS T3 column (3.5 μm , 2.1×50 mm, Waters), a linear gradient with acidified ultrapure water (0.1 vol.-% formic acid), and methanol (HPLC grade, J.T. Baker, USA). The spray voltage was 4000 V, the desolvation temperature was set to 280 °C, and the transfer capillary to 270 °C. Auxiliary and sheath gas were set to 10 and 35 bar, respectively. Due to lacking internal standards, quantification was done using echo peak injection with an XSelect HSS T3 precolumn (2.5 μm , 2.1×5 mm, Waters). The injection volume was 40 μL . Standards and samples were always injected twice, and after 10 samples, a blank and two standards of different concentrations were injected.

Based on previous studies regarding the most dominant MC variants in natural bloom samples and water from the Lalla Takerkoust reservoir (El Ghazali et al., 2011), a standard solution containing a mixture of three MC variants, namely MC-LR, MC-YR, and MC-RR, was obtained from Cyano Biotech GmbH (Berlin, Germany) and diluted using 50 % methanol. The limit of detection (LOD) was 50 ng L^{-1} .

3. Statistical analyses and Landsat image processing

Comprehensive statistical analyses were conducted on the dataset using R version 4.2.2 (2022-10-31 ucrt) (R Core Team, 2023), employing libraries such as dplyr, tidyr, ggpubr, and pgirmess. Descriptive statistics were calculated for each dependent variable in two data blocks: median, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum.

To assess the physicochemical parameters based on sample dates and sites, the Kruskal-Wallis test was performed using the `Kruskal.test()` function from the `pgirmess` library. Significant differences among the physicochemical parameters across sample dates and sites were determined based on a 95 % confidence interval and a 5 % cutoff. Posthoc tests using the `pairwise.Wilcox.test()` function from the `stats` package were conducted for pairwise comparisons, considering multiple simultaneous comparisons. The p-values obtained from the posthoc tests were adjusted using the Benjamini-Hochberg (BH) correction and the `p.adjust()` function in R for multiple testing.

The analysis of the MCs dataset focused on examining the influence of sample sites and dates on MC concentration. Kruskal-Wallis tests were applied to compare MC concentrations among different sample sites and dates, considering the MC variants (MC-LR and MC-YR). Posthoc pairwise comparisons were conducted using appropriate correction methods for multiple comparisons. Dunn's test with Bonferroni correction was applied for sample site comparisons, while the Benjamini-Hochberg (BH) correction was used for sample date comparisons.

To investigate the combined impact of the `Sample_site` and `Sample_date` on the studied variables, a Kruskal-Wallis two-way ANOVA was performed using the `Kruskal.test()` function from the `stats` library. This non-parametric test assessed significant differences between categorical variables and explored their potential interactions.

Correlation analyses examined the relationships between the dependent and independent variables, "Sample_date." The Kruskal-Wallis test was used to identify significant associations, and posthoc pairwise comparisons with Bonferroni correction were performed to explore specific differences between groups or levels concerning the dependent variables. The `pairwise.wilcox.test()` function from the `stats` library was used for these comparisons.

4. Results

4.1. Molecular identification and algae dynamic in the Lalla Takerkoust reservoir

To enhance our understanding of the molecular characterization of the isolated cyanobacteria, a phylogenetic tree (Fig. 2) was constructed. The resulting tree unequivocally demonstrates that these strains can be confidently classified within *Microcystis* and *Synechococcus* genera.

Table 1

m/z values used for the multiple reaction monitoring modus.

Compound	[M + H] ⁺	Daughter m/z	Collision energy (V)	s-lens (V)
MC-RR	520.0	135.0	29	124
		102.9	49	124
		134.9	55	249
MC-LR	995.5	163.2	58	249
		135.0	66	256
MC-YR	1045.5	375.0	51	256

Fig. 2. Molecular Characterization of Cyanobacteria Strains Responsible for Toxic Blooms in the Lalla Takerkoust Reservoir *Microcystis* sp. LT (OQ658602) and *Synechococcus* sp. LT (OQ658601): Maximum Likelihood Phylogenetic Tree of 16S rRNA Sequences using Kimura 2-parameter model, depicting clustering patterns and evolutionary relationships of 18 sequences (1493 positions) in MEGA11.

Algal cell counts per liter varied significantly over time ($p < 0.001$). Dominant species were *Microcystis* (max 93.75 % on November 11th 2019) from September 2019 to March 2020 and *Microcystis* (max 99.47 % on December 28th 2020) from November 2020 to March 2021. Other cyanobacteria and non-cyanobacteria microalgae were present at lower

levels (Fig. 3).

4.2. Cyanobacterial bloom and toxicity of isolated strains

Toxicity of cyanobacterial blooms was assessed by measuring the

Fig. 3. Water bloom and microalgae dynamics in the Lalla Takerkoust reservoir: (a) photograph of the surface bloom, (b) microscopic observation of a sample collected on November 11th, 2019, and (c) temporal dynamics of algal cells during bloom periods from September 16th, 2019 to March 15th, 2020 and November 15th, 2020 to March 23rd, 2021.

concentrations of MC variants, including MC-RR, MC-LR, and MC-YR, in the collected samples. The results given in Table 2 show variations in toxin levels in bloom samples during the sampling period.

Notably, specific samples showed non-detectable levels (ND) of toxins, indicating the absence of toxins in those particular instances. Specifically, the non-toxic *Synechococcus* sp., isolated from the samples, did not produce any detectable MCs.

Highest MC concentrations were observed on November 11th, 2019, and November 22nd, 2020, for MC-LR and MC-YR variants. For MC-RR, the highest levels were detected on November 22nd, 2020. It is worth mentioning that MC-LR consistently exhibited high levels throughout the sampling period, while MC-RR and MC-YR concentrations varied, with the MC-RR only being quantifiable on November 22nd, 2020/sample.

Moreover, cyanobacteria strains were also analyzed for their toxicity (Table 3). *Microcystis* sp. strain isolated on 11th November 2020 showed the presence of all three MC variants with varying concentrations of MC-RR, MC-LR, and MC-YR. The concentration of MC-RR was highest in the strain, followed by MC-LR and MC-YR.

These findings highlight the fluctuating levels of MC variants in cyanobacterial blooms, with the toxic strain *Microcystis* sp. capable of producing multiple MC variants. In contrast, the non-toxic strain *Synechococcus* sp. had no detectable toxins.

4.3. Changes in water physicochemical quality at different sampling sites

The focal point of this study was to assess water quality variations in the Lalla Takerkoust reservoir across diverse sites and dates. The investigation covered two sampling periods: period 1, lasting from September 16th 2019, to March 15th 2020, and period 2, spanning from November 22nd 2020, to March 23rd 2021.

Analysis of carbon-related metrics, such as BOD5 and COD, revealed comparable median values between the two periods, showcasing marginal reductions. Conversely, nitrogen-related variables, particularly TN, demonstrated a slight decrease in the median during period 2 compared to period 1. In contrast, phosphorous-related parameters, exemplified by PO4_P, exhibited a modest increase in the median during period 2.

Significant differences ($p < 0.001$) across sites and dates for COD, NH4, NO3_N, NO2_N, TKN, PO4_P, PH, DO, EC, TDS, BOD5, TN were highlighted through Kruskal–Wallis tests, depicted in Figures S2 and S3. Pairwise comparison using Wilcoxon rank sum tests with continuity correction or exact test confirmed significant differences between different sites for these parameters, and the p -values were adjusted using the Benjamini–Hochberg correction for multiple comparisons to ensure the reliability of obtained results.

4.4. Spatiotemporal fluctuations of MC-LR and MC-YR cyanotoxin levels in the Lalla Takerkoust reservoir water

MC-LR and MC-YR were detected (Fig. 4), with MC-LR's median similar between periods ($2.20 \pm 50.50 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ in period 2 and $2.44 \pm 5.44 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ in period 1). In contrast, MC-YR's median increased in

Table 2
Variations of MC concentrations in natural cyanobacterial bloom samples.

Sample dates	MC-RR $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ Dw	MC-LR $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ Dw	MC-YR $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ Dw
September 16th 2019	ND	1754.11 ± 20.64	1998.72 ± 70.72
October 14th 2019	ND	1702.29 ± 56.95	2711.13 ± 45.57
November 11th 2019	ND	3948.86 ± 81.53	4884.67 ± 34.96
December 09th 2019	ND	3157.41 ± 40.41	2677.48 ± 55.75
November 22th 2020	2096.22 ± 37.56	5167.33 ± 44.33	5059.76 ± 57.79
December 28th 2020	ND	5312.17 ± 23.3	4409.03 ± 50.35
January 20th 2021	ND	3722.63 ± 35.93	3861.80 ± 53.1
February 15th 2021	ND	2446.48 ± 31.77	2223.26 ± 53.03

* ND = not detected.

Table 3

MC variants detected in *Microcystis* sp. lab cultures (dissolved and intracellular).

Sample type	<i>Microcystis</i> sp. dissolved MC ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)	<i>Synechococcus</i> sp. ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ DW)	<i>Microcystis</i> sp. biomass intracellular MC ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ DW)
MC-RR	355.53 ± 4.84	ND	614.16 ± 50.78
MC-LR	133.42 ± 8.61	ND	228.65 ± 26.79
MC-YR	137.19 ± 7.34	ND	238.67 ± 43.31

* ND = not detected.

period 2 ($4.14 \pm 30.953 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) compared to period 1 ($0.084 \pm 4.64 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$).

MC-LR values ranged from 0.05 to $160.39 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ in period 2, observed at the Farm site on March 23rd 2021, and at the reservoir (Dam) site on November 22nd 2020, respectively. In period 1, values ranged from 0.05 to $22.49 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. Regarding MC-YR, values varied from 0.05 to $121.20 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ in period 2, with higher levels at the reservoir and outlet sites.

Analysis of MC-LR and MC-YR differences among sampling sites revealed significant variation ($X^2 = 13.87$, $X^2 = 23.49$, respectively, $p < 0.001$). Specifically, MC-LR varied significantly between the Dam and Farm sites, while for MC-YR, differences were notable between Dam-Exit and Farm sites. Analyzing differences across sampling dates revealed significant variations (χ^2 range: 44.63–136.56, $p < 0.001$), highlighting the necessity of adjusting p -values using the Benjamini–Hochberg correction for robustness.

4.5. Cyanobacteria bloom dynamics: NDVI insights from different years

The NDVI analysis in Fig. 5 sheds light on cyanobacteria bloom variations within the reservoir across years. The median NDVI across all years was 0.135 ± 0.051 , indicating variability. Notably, 2017 had the highest NDVI (0.213 ± 0.106), while 2008 had the lowest (0.109 ± 0.00), showing minimal cyanobacterial growth.

The year 1994 exhibited the most inconsistent NDVI (median: 0.21 ± 0.122 , IQR: 0.232), implying significant variation in cyanobacterial cover. Conversely, 2008 had an IQR of 0.00, suggesting uniform NDVI values and less representativeness. Years like 2001, 2003, and 2004 shared similar median NDVI values (0.132 ± 0.05 , 0.132 ± 0.057 , and 0.133 ± 0.056), indicating consistent cyanobacteria bloom cover. In 2017, outlier NDVI values (0.652, 0.616, 0.600, 0.576) hinted at dense cyanobacterial blooms, potentially due to spatially confined blooms influenced by wind direction.

Examining IQR revealed insights; 2017 had a small IQR (0.136) and a narrower range (0.155 to 0.292), while 1994 had a larger IQR (0.232) and a wider spread (0.12 to 0.352). This suggests varied cyanobacterial cover across the reservoir in different years.

To better understand cyanobacterial bloom dynamics in the Lalla Takerkoust reservoir, we utilized NDVI results for the sampled period in conjunction with limnological data. These findings provide additional information to supplement the extensive analyses conducted over the past 30 years. Fig. 6A illustrates the distribution of NDVI values across three categories: $\text{NDVI} < 0.1$, $\text{NDVI} \leq 0.25$, and $\text{NDVI} > 0.25$ for two distinct sampling periods: period 1 (September 16th, 2019 to March 15th, 2020) and period 2 (November 22nd, 2020, to March 23rd, 2021).

During period 1 (Fig. 6A), most values fell into the $\text{NDVI} < 0.1$ category, with percentage values ranging from 87.2 % on February 8th, 2020, to 99.9 % on March 15th, 2020. $\text{NDVI} \leq 0.25$ category had lower percentage values ranging from 0.084 % on March 15th, 2020, to 12.2 % on January 7th, 2020. $\text{NDVI} > 0.25$ category had negligible percentage values during period 1.

In period 2 (Fig. 6A), there was a significant increase in the percentage values of $\text{NDVI} \leq 0.25$ and $\text{NDVI} > 0.25$ categories. $\text{NDVI} \leq 0.25$ category had percentage values ranging from 5.9 % on January 20th, 2021, to 13.9 % on November 22nd, 2020, with additional peaks

Fig. 4. Relationship between sampling site, date, and variation in the concentration of two variants of MCs grouped by sampling site (Dam, Dam-Exit, Farm), including MC-LR concentration (MC-LR) and MC-YR concentration (MC-YR), asterisks (***) represent statistical significance levels with p -values < 0.001 for Kruskal–Wallis test statistics.

Fig. 5. NDVI Variation in the Lalla Takerkoust reservoir over 30 years: annual patterns in cyanobacteria bloom cover.

occurring in December 2020 and February 2021. NDVI > 0.25 category had percentage values ranging from 0.056 % on several dates to a maximum of 5.8 % on January 20th, 2021, with other significant values occurring on November 22nd, 2020, and December 28th, 2020.

Overall, these findings indicate that during period 1, cyanobacterial bloom coverage in the Lalla Takerkoust reservoir was lower than in period 2.

Moreover, regarding limnological data in the Lalla Takerkoust reservoir, during period 1, the total algal cell counts ranged from 7.98×10^5 to 1.74×10^7 cells L^{-1} , with the highest value recorded on December 09th 2019. Bloom_MC content recorded for September 16th and December 09th 2019, ranged from 3752.82 to 8833.53 μg MCs g^{-1} DW and Water MC content from 0.53 to 18.78 μgL^{-1} , with the highest value

recorded on January 7th, 2020.

During period 2, the total algal cell counts ranged from 1.30×10^6 to 1.29×10^8 cells L^{-1} , with the highest value recorded on December 28th 2020. Bloom_MC content on January 20th, 2021, ranged from 4669.74 to 12,323.30 μg MCs g^{-1} DW, and water MCs content from 0.99 to 160.535 μgL^{-1} , with the highest value recorded on November 22nd, 2020.

Data on NDVI coverage percentages, total algae cell counts, bloom_MC content, and water MCs content confirm that during period 2, there was a significant increase in cyanobacterial blooms in the Lalla Takerkoust reservoir compared to period 1. The high total algal cell counts, bloom_MC content, and water MCs content recorded during period 2 corroborate the high percentage values of NDVI ≤ 0.25 and

Fig. 6. Temporal analysis of cyanobacterial blooms in the Lalla Takerkoust reservoir: NDVI comparison of two distinct periods (Period 1: September 16th, 2019 - March 15th, 2020; Period 2: November 22nd, 2020 - March 23rd, 2021) A); Thirty-year analysis of NDVI subsets revealing historical long-term patterns of cyanobacterial bloom growth and vegetation cover in the Lalla Takerkoust reservoir B).

NDVI > 0.25 categories during the same period. This suggests the presence of moderate and advanced levels of cyanobacteria blooms in the reservoir. The combination of satellite images and limnological data analysis provides strong evidence for the temporal monitoring of cyanobacterial blooms in the Lalla Takerkoust reservoir.

The NDVI data subsets (Fig. 6B) unveiled cyanobacterial bloom patterns in the Lalla Takerkoust reservoir. NDVI values within the range of 0.1 to 0.3 signify an average level of bloom cover, while those exceeding 0.3 indicate dense cyanobacterial blooms. In all years, NDVI values fell within the 0.1 to 0.3 range. However, years like 1995, 1999, 2005, and 2016 maintained consistent cyanobacterial cover within this range, signifying an average level of bloom cover. Conversely, 1994, 1998, 2015–2018, and 2020 exhibited more variable and pronounced cyanobacterial cover with NDVI values above 0.3. Notably, 2001, 2003, and 2004 clustered together, showing sustained similar cyanobacterial bloom cover. Additionally, in 2020, NDVI values exceeded 0.3, indicating dense cyanobacterial blooms.

The NDVI analysis and limnological data highlighted historical cyanobacterial bloom behaviors. Correlation analyses (Fig. 7) revealed NDVI's positive correlation with water toxins, algal cell counts, % Microcystis, PO4_P, NH4_N, NO3_N, and NO2_N (correlation coefficients: 0.35 to 0.57, $p < 0.001$). Conversely, NDVI exhibited negative

correlations with % other cyanobacteria and % non-cyanobacteria microalgae (-0.41 to -0.46, $p < 0.001$).

These findings confirm the association between cyanobacterial abundance, nutrient concentrations, and eutrophication. The dominance of *Microcystis* during blooms aligns with an increase in toxin, potentially impeding the growth of other microalgae. The study underscores the need to comprehend the driving factors behind these phenomena for effective mitigation strategies.

5. Discussion

Studying cyanobacterial harmful algal blooms (CyanoHAB) requires understanding the underlying causes and factors determining their persistence. One crucial aspect is the identification of specific cyanobacteria strains forming those blooms and the parameters promoting their growth (Ogashawara et al., 2016; Romanis et al., 2021). Molecular analyses conducted in our study revealed that cyanobacteria isolates belonged to the genera *Microcystis* and *Synechococcus*. This finding aligns with previous research that has identified *Microcystis* as a common genus associated with CyanoHABs in freshwater environments (Jankowiak et al., 2019; Jiang et al., 2022; Kokarakis et al., 2023; Zamyadi et al., 2021). To explore the dynamics of cyanobacteria blooms and other

Fig. 7. Correlation Analysis of NDVI with Water Nutrients and Cyanobacterial Abundance in Lalla Takerkoust reservoir where Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) (unitless), bloom biomass toxin (Bloom_toxin) ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ DW), water temperature (W_Temp) ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), water toxin concentration (W_Toxin) ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$), total algal cell counts (Algae_Cells) (cells L^{-1}), Microcystis relative abundance (% Microcystis) (%), other cyanobacteria relative abundance (% Other cyanobacteria) (%), non-cyanobacteria microalgae relative abundance (% Microalgae non-Cyano) (%), orthophosphate concentration (PO4) (mg L^{-1}), ammonium (NH4) (mg L^{-1}), nitrate (NO3) (mg L^{-1}), nitrite (NO2) (mg L^{-1}), and organic nitrogen concentration (N.Org) (mg L^{-1}). Asterisks give statistical significance levels for the Pearson correlation test statistics, which were (***) p -values < 0.001, (**) p -values < 0.01, and (*) p -values < 0.05.

microalgae, our study assessed changes in algal cell counts over time, revealing significant differences between different periods. The dominant species also varied over time, with *Microcystis* being the dominant species during peak bloom periods, while other cyanobacterial species and non-cyanobacterial microalgae were prevalent during early and senescence bloom stages. These results are consistent with previous research confirming that *Microcystis aeruginosa* is the dominant species responsible for toxic blooms in the Lalla Takerkoust reservoir (Oudra et al., 2001; Samoudi et al., 2016).

Regarding the kinetics of cells, our study recorded a peak of 1.30×10^8 algal cells per L of total green algae and cyanobacteria. However, a previous study conducted by Samoudi et al. (2016) in the same reservoir found a total of 3.34×10^7 *Microcystis* cells L^{-1} at the reservoir's upstream end (SL1: $31^{\circ}19'35.54''N$ and $8^{\circ}8'28.66''W$, Fig. 1), and 2.08×10^7 *Microcystis* cells L^{-1} at SL2 ($31^{\circ}20'33.62''N$ and $8^{\circ}8'37.90''W$, Fig. 1). These findings indicate that the bloom might vary spatially and have been more pronounced in our study period.

We found significant variations in MC levels over the sampling period and between sites, with some samples having non-detectable levels of toxins. Toxin levels, however, were higher near or in the reservoir and decreased when moving away from the reservoir towards agricultural farms through artificial canals. This finding is consistent with studies that discussed the fate of cyanobacterial toxins in the aquatic environment and their toxicity to aquatic organisms (Chorus and Welker, 2021; Ho et al., 2012; Santos et al., 2020; Song et al., 2007). Furthermore, our study found that the toxic *Microcystis* sp. strain could produce multiple MC variants, while the non-toxic strain *Synechococcus* sp. did not produce any detectable toxins. Strategies for reducing MC toxicity in freshwater ecosystems, such as the use of biological control agents and water treatment technologies, have been discussed (Falda et al., 2023; Mugani et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2021).

Our study revealed that the *Microcystis* strain responsible for blooms in the Lalla Takerkoust reservoir is toxic and produces several MC variants in the laboratory. The strain had mainly three variants, MC-RR, MC-LR, and MC-YR, with total concentrations ranging from 355.53 ± 4.84 to 133.42 ± 8.61 $\mu g L^{-1}$ MC in the dissolved portions. When considering the combination of dissolved and intracellular portions, the strain could produce up to 614.16 ± 50.78 μg MCs g^{-1} DW in the laboratory. It is worth noting that the MC-RR variant was predominantly produced, which is consistent with findings by Oudra et al. (2001, 2002a), who isolated *Microcystis* in the same reservoir, producing only the MC-RR variant in the laboratory (between 650 and 707 μg MC-RR g^{-1} DW). Regarding the dissolved concentration of (MCs) in the reservoir water, our study recorded the highest concentration of 160.44 $\mu g L^{-1}$ MC-LR on November 22nd, 2020. This is substantially higher than the maximum concentration of 95.40 $\mu g L^{-1}$ MCs recorded previously in December 2005 and a concentration of 60.00 $\mu g L^{-1}$ MCs in November 2006 (El Ghazali et al. (2011)).

The observed discrepancies in MC concentrations between laboratory-cultured *Microcystis* strains and natural bloom samples in the Lalla Takerkoust reservoir are noteworthy. Our analyses revealed exceptionally high MC concentrations in natural blooms, reaching up to $12,312$ $\mu g/g$ DW, which may appear unprecedented compared to laboratory-cultured strains. However, this observation is consistent with previous studies indicating that natural blooms often exhibit significantly higher MC concentrations than lab-cultured strains. Previous studies, such as Loudiki et al. (2002) and El Khalloufi et al. (2013), have reported similarly high concentrations of MC in natural blooms from this reservoir, reaching 8800 $\mu g g^{-1}$ DW and $11,500$ μg MC-LR equivalent g^{-1} DW, respectively. Tazart et al. (2021) also demonstrated variability in toxin production, with a *Microcystis* strain isolated from Lalla Takerkoust in 2015 producing lower amounts of MCs (10 $\mu g L^{-1}$) in laboratory conditions. Additionally, the observed differences in MC concentrations between lab-cultured *Microcystis* and natural bloom samples are in line with findings from Oudra et al. (2001, 2002a) and Loudiki et al. (2002), who reported, for instance, that the 1999 natural cyanobacterial bloom

contained 16.76 times more MCs compared to lab-cultured *Microcystis* isolated in the same year.

Other research also revealed that cyanobacterial mats produced higher amounts of microcystin than culturable strains, and this disparity was explained by the presence of many strains in the bloom with varying microcystin concentrations (Ward et al., 1997; Zaki et al., 2020).

In their studies, Oudra et al. (2001) and Oudra et al. (2002b), the authors suggested that *Microcystis* strains isolated from bloom samples from the Lalla Takerkoust reservoir tend to produce fewer MC variants under laboratory conditions than in their natural environment. During our investigation, our strain produced three MC variants, consistent with the natural bloom of the month from which the strain was isolated. However, we observed the absence of MC-RR in both water and bloom samples during all other sampling times, highlighting potential discrepancies between laboratory-cultured strains and natural samples in terms of microcystin production dynamics. This disparity underscores the complexity of *Microcystis* behavior and toxin production, which are influenced by various factors such as environmental conditions and the vertical distribution within the water column. Further research is necessary to gain a comprehensive understanding of these mechanisms.

In our analysis, we found a correlation between NDVI and cyanobacteria toxin concentration during blooms ($r = 0.44$), suggesting that NDVI data can be used as an indicator of cyanobacteria toxin level. Ogashawara et al. (2016) focused on mapping algal blooms in Lake Erie, Ohio, using the slope algorithm and compared results with NDVI. The authors concluded that NDVI might not be advisable for monitoring algal blooms due to its requirement for atmospheric correction. However, NDVI would be helpful where there is little other useful information, such as restoring the past algal bloom dynamics.

In our analysis, we focused on the distribution of NDVI in the Lalla Takerkoust reservoir over 30 years to understand the dynamics of cyanobacterial growth. First, based on our limnological data, we subdivided NDVI into three classes. An NDVI value of <0.1 was classified as indicating water without any detectable cyanobacteria, as described by Cao & Han (2021). NDVI values between 0.1 and 0.25 represented moderate cyanobacterial blooms, while NDVI values greater than 0.25 represented dense cyanobacteria bloom coverage. By correlating NDVI with environmental parameters of the samples, such as total algal cell counts, bloom MC content, and water MC content, this approach provided a comprehensive understanding of the percentage coverage at different stages of cyanobacterial development over the sampling period (2019 to 2021). This allowed us to extend our conclusions to previous years (1991 to 2019).

From our dataset, we found weak positive correlations, ranging from $r = 0.20$ to 0.23 , between air temperature near the water surface and precipitation with NDVI, suggesting that these environmental variables alone may not be solid determinants for the proliferation of cyanobacteria in the Lalla Takerkoust reservoir. While the specific factors contributing to the development of cyanobacterial blooms in the Lalla Takerkoust reservoir remain unclear, studies in other freshwater ecosystems have identified several factors, including land use changes, excessive nutrient inputs, and climate variability (Montero et al., 2021; Rodríguez-Romero et al., 2018). Wan et al. (2014) also showed that urban and agricultural land were essential sources of TN and TP concentrations in the Xitiaoxi River Watershed. Similarly, Zhang et al. (2023) investigated the impact of land-use types on water quality in the Dianchi Lake Basin. They also found that land-use changes affected TN and TP concentrations. Sustainable land use practices and effective nutrient management strategies are crucial in reducing nutrient loads and protecting the health of freshwater ecosystems (Rodríguez-Romero et al., 2018). The authors also identified human settlements and urbanization as sources of high levels of nutrients and fecal coliforms, underlining the importance of managing nutrient inputs to improve water quality, particularly in reservoirs.

Although there is currently no definitive evidence to support direct nutrient inputs of N or P from human activities, including industrial

waste discharge into Lalla Takerkoust reservoir promoting annual CyanoHABs, we hypothesize that initiation of rainfall may enhance the nutrient load in the reservoir, leading to the promotion of CyanoHABs (Aubriot et al., 2020; Mu et al., 2019; Porojan et al., 2020). Specifically, we noted an increase in overall microalgae abundance following initial rains in warm weather conditions, consistent with the anticipated effects of eutrophication.

In addition, we found a positive correlation between water temperature and the percentage of *Microcystis*, with a correlation coefficient of 0.33 and a p-value of <0.05. Furthermore, we observed a strong positive correlation ($r = 0.67$, $p < 0.001$) between the percentage of *Microcystis* and N and P concentrations in the water. These findings suggest that nutrient concentrations and water temperature together are important determinants driving CyanoHABs in the Lalla Takerkoust reservoir.

Moreover, our study highlights the potential negative impact of CyanoHABs on other types of algae and cyanobacteria. The observed negative correlation between NDVI and the percentages of other cyanobacteria and non-cyanobacterial microalgae implies that a *Microcystis* bloom hinders the growth of other algae and cyanobacteria species. This finding aligns with prior studies investigating the allelopathic effects of *Microcystis* on other phytoplankton species (Paerl and Otten, 2013; Śliwińska-Wilczewska et al., 2022). Allelopathy, which involves releasing chemicals by one species that negatively influence the growth and survival of different species in the same environment, provides a plausible explanation for this negative correlation.

To validate our satellite-based long-term results, in addition to our conclusions based on short-term data of this study, we compared these data with limnological truth data (Table S1) on cyanobacterial MC cell concentrations during bloom events of previous studies (El Ghazali et al., 2011b; El Khalloufi et al., 2012; Oudra et al., 2002a, 2001; Samoudi et al., 2016). Here, we considered moderate blooms to be between 0.1 and 0.3 and NDVI values above 0.3 to represent dense blooms, as reported by Qin et al. (2022). We noted that Lalla Takerkoust Reservoir has been experiencing bloom events in most years, with some years being more eutrophic than others. For example, in 2008, the NDVI value was the lowest, resulting in the lowest total MC concentration of $432.7 \mu\text{g g}^{-1} \text{DW}$.

Furthermore, in their study, Ogashawara et al. (2016) conducted a study utilizing limnological data and Landsat images to establish a classification system for bloom severity. Their research identified key characteristics that distinguish heavy and moderate blooms. In the case of a heavy bloom, several factors are observed. Firstly, a substantial layer of algae forms on the water surface. Additionally, the cyanobacterial cell count exceeds $1 \times 10^8 \text{ cellsL}^{-1}$, and detectable levels of cyanotoxins are present in the water. Conversely, a moderate bloom exhibits slightly different attributes. Visible cyanobacteria are present within the water column, but no scum formation is observed on the water surface. Moreover, the cyanobacterial cell count falls within the range of 1×10^7 to $1 \times 10^8 \text{ cellsL}^{-1}$.

Based on these findings, we confirm that in the Lalla Takerkoust reservoir, the bloom ranged between moderate to severe with cyanobacterial cell counts of up to $1.29 \times 10^8 \text{ cellsL}^{-1}$, and toxins persisting during the entire year-long even at low cell counts ($1 \times 10^5 \text{ cellsL}^{-1}$; Redouane et al., 2023). Furthermore, it is essential to note that the distribution of cyanobacterial bloom biomass on the historical NDVI map (Fig. 5) is consistent with those conducted by Samoudi et al. (2016), targeting the horizontal distribution of *Microcystis* cells. The authors demonstrate that, depending on the wind direction, the highest *Microcystis* cell numbers were found in the upstream part of the reservoir, particularly at the SL1 and SL2 sampling sites. Furthermore, the temporal analysis of water quality parameters showed significant differences across different sampling dates for all parameters, including MC-LR and MC-YR concentrations. Significant differences in water quality parameters across various sampling sites further imply the influence of local factors, such as land use and hydrological conditions, on cyanobacterial growth and toxin production.

Kruskal-Wallis test and posthoc pairwise comparisons indicate significant variations in the concentrations of MC-LR and MC-YR in the Lalla Takerkoust reservoir across different sampling sites. Notably, both toxins were found to have considerably higher concentrations at the reservoir (Dam) and reservoir-exit (Dam_Exit) sites than at the farm sites. This finding highlights the directionality of toxin reduction from the production site to the place of water use. Specifically, MC-LR concentration decreases by a factor of 5.39 from the reservoir to the agricultural farm, ca. 4 km away. Similarly, for the same distance, the concentration of MC-YR at the farm decreases by a factor of 2.98. Our results fully agree with previous research by Yang et al. (2016), who evaluated the risk of wells close to Lake Chaohu compared to those farther away from this eutrophic lake. They established a positive correlation between well distance and the quantity of MCs during their transfer following penetration.

There are several explanations for the reduction of toxins from the reservoir to the final water users. Firstly, water canals, often dug in the ground, may cause strong MC adsorption to soil particles (Chaffin et al., 2022; Redouane et al., 2019) or infiltration into the soil. Additionally, contact between water and soil microorganisms could accelerate MC biodegradation (Chen et al., 2008; Manage et al., 2009; Santos et al., 2022; Thees et al., 2019). Exposure to macrophytes and sunlight in the channeled water may also contribute to the degradation and photodegradation by natural UV radiation (Wörmer et al., 2010), affecting the reduction of MC concentrations based on exposure duration and distance (Shingai and Wilkinson, 2023). Furthermore, photodegradation is supported by the study conducted by Vione & Rosario-Ortiz. (2021), which investigated the photodegradation kinetics of MC-LR in the epilimnion in the presence of the triplet states of chromophoric dissolved organic matter (CDOM*). They conclude that these organic compounds enhance MC photodegradation.

In our case, CDOM* could arise from the fact that, over the 4 km distance covered by the water from the reservoir to the farm, the hole water drainages are exposed to UV light. This means that the water flows over open, muddy, or concrete structures and comes in contact with organic wastes dumped into the canals during water transit. As a result, the CDOM* content in the water may be high, which could enhance MC photodegradation, as observed previously.

At this stage of the study, however, it remains unclear why MC-LR experiences a more significant reduction compared to MC-YR, even though the former is known to be more stable. This reduction may depend on the initial concentration, which was higher for MC-LR than for MC-YR.

Interestingly, we observed that MC distribution follows a depth pattern. MC-LR dominates at the water surface, while MC-YR prevails in the water outflow point of the reservoir (Dam_Exit), located at a depth of 10 m. This result aligns with previous research by Köker et al. (2021, 2022) and Wilkinson et al. (2020), which showed a vertical distribution of cyanotoxins. This raises concerns about the risk of using water from the reservoir, as the level of contamination of different MC variants can increase at the reservoir outlet. Therefore, without monitoring toxin levels along the water canal, solely analyzing surface water could lead to misleading conclusions, e.g., missing the presence of dominant MC variants at the outlet site, which could be transported to water users and cause risk issues.

6. Conclusion

Cyanobacterial blooms are a significant global threat that poses risks to public health and the freshwater environment. This comprehensive study analyzed the dynamics of cyanobacterial blooms and MC production in the Lalla Takerkoust reservoir, Morocco using various advanced methods. A three-year sampling period –September 2019 to March 2020 and November 2020 to March 2021– identified nutrient concentrations, including PO₄-P, NH₄-N, NO₃-N, and NO₂-N, as critical factors promoting cyanobacterial growth. Interestingly, *Microcystis*

blooms hindered the development of other algae and cyanobacteria species. Dissolved MC concentration significantly varied over time, with peak concentrations ranging from non-detectable levels to 160 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ in November 2020. Moreover, intracellular MC concentrations extracted from lyophilized *Microcystis* natural blooms ranged from 433 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ DW in 2008 to 12,323 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ DW in 2020. Thereby, the toxic strain of *Microcystis* sp. produces multiple MC variants. To assess cyanobacterial blooms and toxin dynamics comprehensively, the study integrated remote sensing techniques, such as Landsat, with limnological data, showing the qualitative transition for cyanobacterial blooms and toxins over different time periods. There was a high potential risk of toxin transfer to the surrounding farms through irrigation water, whereby the concentration of MCs decreased as the distance traveled by irrigation water increased. Yet, the risk of toxin transfer farther away from the bloom source to the field remained high during bloom events. Our study emphasizes the potential risk linked to persistent MC variants found even farther from the reservoir, with significant MC concentrations reaching the fields via irrigation water. This underscores the necessity for further research on the fate and transport of MC variants in freshwater ecosystems. Based on our findings, effective management strategies are crucial to minimizing the risk of toxin transfer to human consumption and ensuring public health and safety. Implementing biological control agents and water treatment technologies can assist in reducing MC toxicity in freshwater ecosystems. Additionally, continuous monitoring and ongoing research efforts are required to deepen our understanding of intricate interactions between cyanobacteria, nutrients, and various environmental factors. This knowledge will facilitate the development of effective management strategies to mitigate the risk of cyanobacterial blooms and their associated health risks.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Richard Mugani: Writing – original draft, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Fatima El Khalloufi:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Minoru Kasada:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **El Mahdi Redouane:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Mohammed Haida:** Investigation. **Roseline Prisca Aba:** Methodology, Investigation. **Yasser Essadki:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Soukaina El Amrani Zerfifi:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Sven-Oliver Herter:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis. **Abdessamad Hejjaj:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Faissal Aziz:** Formal analysis. **Naaila Ouazzani:** Supervision. **Joana Azevedo:** Methodology, Formal analysis. **Alexandre Campos:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Anke Putschew:** Validation. **Hans-Peter Grossart:** Validation. **Laila Mandi:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Vitor Vasconcelos:** . **Brahim Oudra:** Writing – original draft, Supervision, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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